

**INDICATORS OF INCREASING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF
INVESTMENTS IMPLEMENTED ON THE BASIS OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE
PARTNERSHIP**

Kadyrov Jasurbek Sharofitdinovich

Tashkent State University of Economics,

independent researcher

E-mail: Bek-maf@mail.ru

Annotation: Throughout this article, you can see that public-private entrepreneurship is considered an excellent way to increase the economic efficiency of investments. By pooling the resources and expertise of both the public and private sectors, projects can be designed and implemented more effectively and efficiently. This can lead to higher returns on investment and a more sustainable economy. Many examples and solutions are given throughout the article.

Key words: Investment project, Effectiveness, population employment, foreign currency, efficiency.

The financial and economic evaluation of the investment project occupies a central place in the process of selection and justification of possible options for placing funds in various operations (objects) with real assets. The financial analysis reveals the possibilities of achieving the results that should be achieved in the implementation of the project based on the goals of each of its participants. In the economic analysis, it is analyzed from the point of view of the effect of the project on the national economy. In particular, World Bank employees (experts) conduct extensive analysis for each project to determine whether it is more effective than other conflicting options for deploying specific resources to the economy¹.

¹ Банковское дело и финансирования инвестиций, /Под редакции Н.Брука. Институт экономического развития Всемирного банка, 1-том, 2-часть, 1995. – С. 281\

G. Birman, S. Schmidt paid special attention to the following in the economic evaluation of investment projects²:

the impact of the project on the development of the national economy is evaluated;

inputted resources and received products are evaluated at uncertain prices that reflect their true value for the national economy;

the analysis includes aspects that directly affect the economy (imports, exports, population employment, foreign currency, supply and demand, environmental conditions, etc.), as well as indirect effects (impact on other areas, etc.);

social conditions are taken into account, etc.

I.I. Mazur, V.D. Shapiro, N.G. Olderogge defined the effectiveness of investment projects as follows: "Effectiveness of investment projects is a category that shows the conformity of the project with the goals and interests of its participants³".

Accordingly, it is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of the project as a whole, as well as to determine the effectiveness of each participant participating in the project. V. According to Berents, P. Khavraneks, in countries with a developed market economy, methods based on evaluating the efficiency of investment projects and comparing them are widely used⁴.

One of the important tasks of the state, enterprises and organizations is to increase the economic efficiency of investments. The essence of the problem of increasing the economic efficiency of investments is that it is necessary to achieve an increase in the volume of production, services and profit, as well as the national

² Бирман Г., Шмидт С. Экономический анализ инвестиционных проектов М.: - Банки и биржи ЮНИТИ, 1997. – С . 613.

³ Мазур И.И., Шапиро В.Д., Ольдерогге Н.Г. М12 Управление проектами: Учебное пособие / Под общ. ред. И.И. Мазура. — 2-е изд. — М.: Омега-Л, 2004 — с. 664

⁴ Беренц В., Хавранекс П. Руководство по оценке эффективности инвестиций, пер.с англ. А.П. Белых, М.: - Инфра-М, 1995. – С. 60-80. Богатин Ю.В., Швандар В.А. "Инвестиционный анализ": Учебное пособие для вузов.-М.: ЮНИТИ-ДАНА, 2000. – С. 142-162.

income, for each cost unit (labor, material, financial). It is known that the terms "efficiency" and "effectiveness" can be often found in micro and macro economy and their sectors. They differ from each other depending on their economic nature and content. The concept of "Effectiveness" reflects the result (achieving a positive result) of the measures used in some part (link) of the economic process. Efficiency is an absolute indicator that shows the economic results of production.

A project will never be implemented unless it provides:

- reimbursement of the invested funds from the income received from the sale of project goods and services;
- that the profit that ensures the profitability of investments is higher than the level of desire of the firm;
- that the payback period of the investment corresponds to the period suitable for the firm.

Determining the validity of achieving such results in investment processes is the main task of determining the financial and economic indicators of any project with funds invested in real assets. Carrying out such an assessment is always a somewhat difficult task, as it requires taking into account the influence of a number of important factors⁵:

- first, investment costs can be made only once or several times over a long period of time;
- secondly, the period of obtaining results from the implementation of the investment project is long and long;
- thirdly, the implementation of long-term operations can lead to an increase in uncertainty and the emergence of risk in the assessment of all aspects of investments.

It is important to remember the features of the discounting process⁶:

⁵ Бозоров Р.Х.-Ўзбекистонда инвестиция лойиҳаларининг иқтисодий самарадорлигини баҳолашни такомиллаштириш "Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар" илмий электрон журнали. № 2, март-апрель, 2018 йил 2/2018 (№ 00034) www.iqtisodiyot.uz

⁶ Финансовый менеджмент: учебник для академического бакалавриата / Г. Б. Поляк [и др.]; ответственный редактор Г. Б. Поляк. - 4-е изд., перераб. и доп. Москва: Издательство Юрайт, 2019. - С. 163

- the moment of reduction may not correspond to the current time for the project;
- cash flows must be expressed in current or deflated prices and in a single currency.

The discounting method is the main basis for calculating dynamic performance indicators as a mechanism for adjusting the future value of cash flows to the current moment⁷:

1. Net present value (net present value) - like net income, it is an indicator that describes the value of project income in terms of value, but takes into account the depreciation process of money over time:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{CF_t}{(1+E)^t} - \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{I_t}{(1+E)^t}$$

Projects with an estimated value of $NPV \leq 0$ are unsuitable projects for participants, potentially efficient projects have a value of $NPV > 0$.

2. The discounted payback period of investments allows to determine the period of recovery of investment costs, but taking into account different monetary costs at different times:

$$DPB = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{I_t}{(1+E)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{CF_t}{(1+E)^t}} \times T$$

3. Discounted investment profitability index - the indicator is similar to a simple recovery index in its meaning and describes the degree to which each unit of funds invested in the project is covered by the income generated by it:

$$DPI = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{CF_t}{(1+E)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^T \frac{I_t}{(1+E)^t}}$$

If the value of $DPI \leq 1, 0$, then the project does not bring the required income to its participants in the specified period, which determines that its implementation is not

⁷ А.С.Клевкова / Основные показатели эффективности инвестиционных проектов, как основа принятия инвестиционных решений. Международный научный журнал «Символ науки», № 1-2 / 2022

appropriate or the initial parameters of the project (investments, income, expenses) need to be revised. implementation period). Projects with $DPI > 1.0$ are accepted for implementation.

4. The internal rate of return is an indicator that reflects the value of the discount rate, where the value of positive net current cash flows is the discounted value of the investment investment, that is, the NPV value of the project is equal to 0. The indicator is used to determine the critical cost of capital for the project.

The following standard formula is used to determine Irr:

$$IRR = E_1 + \frac{NPV_{E_1}}{NPV_{E_1} - NPV_{E_2}} \times (E_2 - E_1)$$

where $E_1 - NPV_{E_1} > 0$ is the value of the discount rate;

E_2 -discount rate value, in this $NPV_{E_2} > 0$;

NPV_{E_1} - E_1 NPV value at the discount rate;

NPV_{E_2} - E_2 NPV value at the discount rate.

In conclusion, we emphasize that all selected projects must ensure real commercial efficiency of the private partner. If the indicators meet the requirements of the concessionaires, they will start concluding contracts for the implementation of the project. Акс ҳолда, ушбу тижорат самарадорлигининг қиймати хусусий инвестицияларни қисқартириш (юқорида муҳокама қилинган механизм) ёки концессия муддатини узайтириш ёки концессионер учун мақбул бўлган тижорат самарадорлиги олинмагунча оширилади.

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